

USE OF MUSIC FOR AUDIENCE ENGINEERING BY LOVEFM, COOL FM, ANDWAZOBIAFM: A COMPARATIVE EVALUATION

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Abstract: This study comparatively evaluated and analyzed the use of music as a tool for engineering audiences on Love 97.7 FM, Cool 96.5 FM, and Wazobia 94.1 FM. The objectives were to determine the genres of music played by Love97.7 FM, Cool 96.5 FM, and Wazobia94.1 FM to engineer the audience. In addition, the study sought to determine whether Love 97.7FM, Cool 96.5FM, and Wazobia 94.1FM had deliberate policies on engineering audiences toward their radio stations through music. The theoretical underpinning of the study was anchored on active audience theory and uses and gratification theory. The design used in the study was a focus group discussion, and the researcher were the instrument for data collection. The sampling was done in two groups, with one focusing on selected staff members from the three different radio stations while the other focused on residents of the Port Harcourt metropolis, out of which a sample size of 15 was chosen with the purposive sampling technique. The three radio stations that were evaluated had audience engineering programs through music, such as the Drivetime Show on Cool 96.5 FM, the One Nigeria Radio show on Love97.7 FM, and the Lunch hour drive on Wazobia 94.1 FM. From the findings of the study, it was discovered that the genres of music, differently put, had played to engineer audiences toward their radio stations. In addition, Love 97.7 FM, Cool 96.5 FM, and Wazobia 94.1 FM had certain financial, musical, and governmental policies attached to their airplay to draw the audience through to their radio stations. In conclusion, from this research, recommendations are that these three radio stations should choose the appropriate genres of music that will facilitate audience engineering on their different radio platforms. Also, Love 97.7 FM, Cool 96.5 FM, and Wazobia 94.1FM FM should learn to take deliberate policies that will help them in audience engineering, especially by reviewing the music played by their stations regularly. Furthermore, Love97.7 FM, Cool 96.5 FM, and Wazobia 94.1 FM should learn to play the right music in order not to cause a nuisance or be seen as generating noise, which eventually leads to the audience switching over to another radio station frequency.

INTRODUCTION

The major interest of any radio station is that individuals tune in to their programs and stick with their station's content. From a financial perspective, those who tune in and listen play a major role in contributing to the economic stance of the radio station; hence, the priority for a radio station is, therefore, to get people to listen to their programs while not switching to another station or turning off the radio. An important element that enables a listener to stick to the radio content is making quality

music programs or playing trending songs. As a result, when people like a radio program, especially the music, they are more likely to stick with that radio station.

According to Schellenberg (2004), a way to explain how radio stations offer positive assessment through their music programs is through the concept of flow. Thus, flow is an idea tussle between the trial of a task and the expertise required of the individual to undertake that task, all of which leads to a particular gratifying mental state. Therefore, it is this same pattern of flow that enables music to bring development to the radio station by increasing their audience rating and making room for more people to run commercials with the radio station. In addition, music being played on the radio actively pushes content to its audience and successfully creates a familiar tune into the listeners' subconscious mind by airing repetitive series of songs corresponding to its scheduled programs.

It is no wonder these days why young people are so in love with music, because songs they love trend on the charts of technological digital musical streaming platforms and as such are always searching on the radio for stations that will play their favourite tunes depending on their mood, it is not a doubt that there are stations that are genre focused in the selection of their music, while some radio stations play classic records, others play commercial songs that are currently in the trend, another may decide to focus its melody on jazz or rhythm and blues, while one more may play afro beats or just hip hop; however it goes, the millennial generation and counting, add up to the audience of a radio station with huge numbers and their core devotion is the music being played on the radio.

Furthermore, Coincina and Biasutti (2013) believe that a radio station remains the number one cradle for the discovery of new songs. Technological advancements and the assistance of internet-enabled devices have been able to expose and expand the horizons of music search and are also providing new ways for radio stations to deliver their content, most notably via streaming. Moreover, the music industry is continuously varying and evolving, and the role that radio plays as a mast of music has modified and reformed with the times. Radio now symbolizes a form of connection through exposure, uniqueness, and duration, which means that there is no better time to use all of the prospects that radio shows have to offer.

In addition, Linbald and De Boise (2019) state that of all media platforms, radio remains the prominent reach platform with about 93% of people tuning to AM/FM radio, which is higher than the number of people using devices such as television, smartphones, and tablets. They also state that 93% of the existing generation listen to radio 10 h per week or more because it provides convenience, flexibility, and understanding for listeners, and this in turn can also present artists with a unique opportunity to get in front of a wider audience. Many people tune in to radio stations because of their familiarity and the fact that they enjoy the type of music being played. This in turn affords a ready-made setting where they can be visible to new radio shows of the same genre.

Radio shows enable a different pattern of being noticed because not everyone has the capability and capacity to be aired but only artists of a certain quality. These artists are viewed as appropriate for each station's audience, and as such are featured. This guarantees quality content programing and a sustained listenership both for the station as well as the artist because it remains one of the best ways that humans can express themselves through ads thoroughly. Music has a crucial role in human life

because everyone likes to listen to it and the radio makes it available all the time; hence, people are attracted to the particular radio station that plays good music. Also, music engineers the audience because a lot of people tune in to the radio searching for mental peace, satisfaction, health, more attention, and the possibility to have positive thoughts. Equally, music has brought development to radio because it has the power to shape cultures and societies around the world and can be passed down from generation to generation.

According to Mehr et al. (2019), music plays a very prominent role in audience engineering because it remains a vital aspect of all human growth and has the power to emotionally, morally, and ethnically impact society. When there is an exchange of songs, especially from one culture to another, they gain valuable insight and learn and lean into another human's way of life. Thus, the effect and impact music has had on audience engineering cannot be denied, as it has been found in every known culture since the beginning of time. Music has evolved to become a fundamental part of human life, and the human mind has evolved to perceive music as the universal language we all speak. All these were made possible through radio broadcasting, and Love FM, COOL FM, and Wazobia FM in Port Harcourt are some these radio stations.

Statement of the Problem

Music represents an enjoyable activity in itself, but its influence goes beyond simple amusement. Listening to music, singing, playing (formally or informally), creating, exploring, composing, and improvising, whether individually or collectively, are common activities for most people. Furthermore, the different sounds of music are characterized by reasons that include skill, creative expertise, and availability of technological resourcefulness. Some reasons why people listen to music include personal enjoyment, creative expression, social connection, and relaxation. However, the music industry is constantly evolving, and the preferences of listeners are constantly changing. This means that radio stations such as LoveFM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM need to adapt their programing to stay relevant and keep their audience engaged.

However, the changing tastes of the audience and the rise of other forms of media present a challenge to radio stations like Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM. These radio stations need to find ways to keep their audiences engaged and interested. One way to achieve this is through "audience engineering," or the strategic use of music to attract and retain an audience. This study provides a comparative evaluation of the use of music for audience engineering by Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to provide a comparative evaluation of the use of music for audience engineering by Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM in Rivers State. The specific objectives were as follows:

1. Determine the genres of music played to engineer audiences by Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM in the Rivers State
2. Determine if Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM had deliberate policies on audience engineering through music

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. What are the impacts of the genres of music played for audience engineering by Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM in Rivers State?
2. What are the types of policies on music being used by Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM in audience engineering?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Several theories are available for this study, but the researchers consider the Active Audience Theory to be appropriate.

Stuart Hall's Active Audience Theory of 1973

Active Audience Theory was proposed by Stuart Hall in 1973. He argues that media audiences do not just receive information passively but are actively involved, often unconsciously, in making sense of the message within their personal and social contexts (Clarke, 2018). Decoding a media message may therefore be influenced by factors such as family background, beliefs, values, culture, interests, education, and experiences. Decoding a message indicates how well a person can effectively receive and understand a message. Active Audience Theory is particularly associated with mass media usage and is a branch of Stuart Hall's Encoding and Decoding Model.

Hall in Wood (2014) noted that audiences were active and not passive when looking at people who were trying to make sense of media messages. Active is when an audience engages, interprets, and responds to media messages and can question the message. Passive is when an audience accepts a message without question and, by doing so, is directly affected by it. Hall in Xie et al. (2022) further emphasized the relationship between the sender and receiver while considering various factors of how the message is interpreted. Hall claims that the audience dictates whether a message is successful or not and found that an audience can alter the meaning of a message to support the social context in which they are in. As a result, Hall concluded that the message encoded by the sender is not always going to be the message that will be decoded by the audience, as in the instance of the Encoding/decoding model. Encoding is what allows a person to be able to understand a given message, while decoding is how well a person can understand the given message when it is received. Hall emphasizes that even though the sender of a message may feel that it will be interpreted clearly, the interpreted message is dependent on how the audience understands it.

Active audience theory is seen as a direct contrast to the effects traditions; however, there are arguments against discounting the effect or influence media can have on an audience, acknowledging that an active audience does not mean that media effect or influence is not possible. This theory is relevant to the study because the decoding of a media message may therefore be influenced by factors such as family background, beliefs, values, culture, interests, education, and experiences. The present study emphasizes the use of music for audience engineering by Cool FM, Love FM, and Wazobia FM in Rivers State.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Music

Music can be defined as an art form that combines sound, harmony, and rhythm. It is a form of communication that can be enjoyed, appreciated, and analyzed (Encyclopædia Britannica, 2022). Music is created and experienced in various ways, from live performances to recorded media and digital files. It can be composed for a specific purpose, such as a film score or a dance piece, or it can be created purely for enjoyment. Music is a universal language that can be enjoyed by people of all ages, cultures, and backgrounds (Merriam-Webster, 2022). It has the power to evoke emotion, express ideas, and create a sense of connection between people. In addition, music can be used to convey messages, tell stories, and promote social change. While it is hard to define the exact elements that make up music, it is often defined by its use of pitch, rhythm, harmony, melody, and other sonic elements. Whether instrumental or vocal, fast or slow, simple or complex, music is a powerful force that connects people and cultures around the world.

The evolution of music also played a central role during the formation of academic musicology in the late nineteenth century. Rehding (2000) stated that during the twentieth century, theoretical and political implications of evolution were heavily debated, leading evolution to fall out of favor in musicology and cultural anthropology. In the twenty-first century, refined concepts of biological evolution were reintroduced to musicology through the work of psychologists of music if the biological evolution of the capacity to make and experience music ("evolution of musicality") has returned as an important topic of contemporary musicological research (Wallin, 2000; Huron, 2006; Patel, 2008; Lawson, 2012; Tomlinson, 2013, 2015; Honing, 2018). Although the concept of cultural evolution of music itself ("musical evolution") remains largely undeveloped by musicologists, despite an explosion of recent research on cultural evolution in related fields such as linguistics, the absence of these refined concepts of biological evolution through musicology has been especially prominent in ethnomusicology, but is also observable in historical musicology and other subfields of musicology (Savage, 2019).

One major exception was the two-volume special edition of *The World of Music*, which was devoted to a critical analysis of Victor Grauer's (2006) essay entitled "Echoes of Our Forgotten Ancestors" (later expanded into book form in Grauer, 2011). Grauer (2011) proposed that the evolution and global dispersal of the human song style parallels the evolution and dispersal of anatomically modern humans out of Africa and that certain groups of contemporary African hunter-gatherers retain the ancestral singing style shared by all humans tens of thousands of years ago. The evolutionary biologist Alan Lomax, who contributed to this publication, found the concept of musical evolution sufficiently self-evident that they simply opened their contribution by stating: "Songs, like genes and languages, evolve" (p. 43).

Music as an agent of Audience Engineering

Consciousness, as we know it, is birthed from the established idea of movement within the bodily organism. These movements spark the familiarity and operation of the globe in which we find ourselves. These births of consciousness are detailed in our animalistic evolution, which is in the past, these

growth births of our evolution have developed new cooperation, and artistic embankments which have been in a regulation by us due to our feelings and expressions which stem from the vital signs within us as living organisms, according to Sherrington the neurophysiologist, with his published facts on muscle excitation in 1955, then concluded Panksepp in 1998 with his theories on affective neuroscience as well as neuroscientist Antonio Damasio in his book *The Feeling of What Happens* in 2003, also in the book, *The Singing Neanderthals* by Steven Mithen in 2005, Daniel Stern in his book *The Issue of Vitality* in 2010 particularly from pages 88-102 and the joint article by Eisenberg and Sulik titled *Emotion-Related Self-Regulation in Children* published in 2012.

The genres of music played by Love FM, CoolFM, and Wazobia FM to engineer audiences can vary but typically include a mix of genres such as pop, hip-hop, R&B, rock, country, electronic, and more. Each station may have a different focus on certain genres based on its target audience, but they typically include a variety of genres to appeal to various listeners. For example, the genres commonly played by Love FM, CoolFM, and Wazobia FM are; Pop: Justin Bieber, Harry Styles, Ariana Grande, BTS, Dua Lipa, Adele, and the Weeknd are just a few examples of pop artists frequently played by these stations. Hip-Hop: Drake, Kendrick Lamar, Lil Nas X, Megan Thee Stallion, Cardi B, and Juice WRLD are among the many hip-hop artists who are often heard on Love FM, CoolFM, and Wazobia.

Pop Music: this is a genre of popular music that typically has a catchy, upbeat sound with mainstream appeal. It often incorporates elements of other genres, such as rock, R&B, and dance music. Some of the defining characteristics of pop music include repetitive lyrics, strong melodies, and a focus on mass appeal.

Hip-hop: This genre of music originated in the Bronx, New York, and is rooted in African American and Caribbean cultures. It typically often consists

R&B, or rhythm and blues, is a genre of popular music that combines elements of soul, funk, and gospel music. It is often characterized by smooth, soulful vocals and a slow, steady beat.

Rock Music: This broad genre incorporates elements of blues, pop, and folk music. It typically features electric guitars, drums, and bass, and its vocal style ranges from aggressive to melodic.

Country Music: This genre is rooted in the folk music traditions of the American South and Southwest. It often features steel guitars, fiddles, and banjos, and its lyrics typically focus on themes of rural life and relationships.

Electronic music, or EDM, is a genre of music that uses electronic instruments, such as synthesizers and drum machines, to create its sound. It encompasses various styles, from house and techno to substep and trance. Rock, country, and electronic music all fall under the larger umbrella of popular music, which is defined as music that appeals to various people and is often commercially successful.

Jazz: This music genre originated in the early 20th-century in the United States, drawing on African American musical traditions. It typically features improvisation syncopated rhythms, and a combination of brass and woodwind instruments. Some famous jazz artists include Louis Armstrong, Duke Ellington, and Miles Davis.

Reggae: This is a music genre that developed in Jamaica in the 1960s. It is characterized by a slow, relaxed tempo and the use of instruments such as the guitar, drums, and bass. It often incorporates elements of African, Caribbean, and American music

Classical Music: This broad term encompasses various musical styles, but it typically refers to music from the Western art music tradition. It can include genres such as opera, symphony, and chamber music and is often composed and performed according to specific rules and conventions. Some famous classical composers include Mozart, Beethoven, and Bach.

Love FM, Cool FM and Wazobia FM Deliberate Policies on Audience Engineering Through Music

The policies of Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM regarding audience engineering through music vary based on the station's target audience and programming style. Love FM, for example, is a station that specializes in romantic ballads and pop music, and they strive to create a relaxing and inviting atmosphere for their listeners. Cool FM, on the other hand, focuses on contemporary hits and appeals to a younger demographics with high-energy, upbeat programming. Wazobia FM, a Nigerian-based station, plays a mix of local and international music, with an emphasis on traditional Nigerian sounds and styles (Love FM, n.d; Cool FM, n.d; Wazobia FM, n. d.).

As for their specific policies on audience engineering, Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM all use their music programming to create a certain atmosphere for their listeners. Love FM, for example, plays music designed to be romantic and relaxing, and their DJs often speak in a soft, soothing tone. Cool FM, on the other hand, uses upbeat music and energetic announcers to keep their listeners engaged and entertained. Wazobia FM takes a slightly different approach, incorporating local languages and cultural elements into its programming to appeal to its audience.

In addition to their musical programming, Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM use other methods to attract their target audiences. Love FM, for example, offers a "Love Lounge" feature where listeners can request songs for their loved ones and share messages of affection. Cool FM uses social media platforms such as Instagram and Twitter to engage with their audience and share content that is relevant to their interests. Wazobia FM has a "Hello Wazobia" segment where listeners can call in and share their thoughts and experiences. All three stations also have interactive websites and mobile apps that allow listeners to connect with each other (Love FM, n.d; Cool FM, n.d; Wazobia FM, n. d.).

Review of Related Empirical Studies

A study of Wazobia FM listeners in Lagos, Nigeria" by Adewale and Alafolu (2018). The study used a survey to collect data from a sample of Wazobia FM listeners in Lagos, Nigeria. The study found that Wazobia FM listeners were highly engaged with the station's programming with over 80% of respondents saying they listen to the station for at least an hour each day. Additionally, the study found that listeners were highly satisfied with the station's programming with over 70% of respondents rating the station as "excellent in terms of its overall quality. Overall, the study found that the station's ability to engage listeners through its interactive programming was a key factor in its success.

Another study that explored audience engagement and interest was understanding the motivations of radio listeners in Nigeria: The Case of Cool FM" by Ogbu and Okeke (2015). This study used a survey

to collect data from a sample of Cool FM listeners in Nigeria. The study found that the most common motivation for listening to Cool FM was the station's interactive and engaging programming. Additionally, the study found that Cool FM listeners were motivated by the station's unique music selection, which featured a mix of international and local music. The study also found that the station's interactive elements, such as competitions and giveaways, played a role in motivating listeners to interact with the station. These interactive elements allowed listeners to participate in the station's programming and feel like they were part of the station's community. This sense of community was another motivating factor for listeners, as it allowed them to feel connected to other listeners and the station itself. Therefore, in addition to the station's unique programming and music selection, its interactive elements and sense of community were key factors in motivating listeners to tune in.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study framework was the focus group discussion (FGD), a technique of the qualitative research method that thrives on the use of open-ended questions to provide a small group of participants. In the focus group discussion, questions asked to participants were filtered to elicit responses relating to the participant's beliefs, opinions, reactions, and perceptions of the musical concept. In this particular method of research applied as here, the focus group discussion was chosen to enable the researcher to capture participants' views and disposition toward the use of music for audience engineering and how these radio stations, Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM, inspired or engaged the audience through their musical content.

Sample Size

The sample for this study could have been identified using the checkmarket.com online sample size calculator, or even Taro Yamane or Krejcie and Morgan, which is an online table determinant for sample sizes, but due to the qualitative approach involved, and aided with the purposive sampling technique, the sample size for this research involved only 15 fifteen chosen participants, who have undergone a prior relationship of communication with the researcher and given the creative space of this research, as it involves music and a loyal listenership as well as an experienced understanding of the administration that goes on in that area of audio journalism, it was of dire necessity because the population itself without being sampled was enormously vast and would lead to a lot of incorrect data which would misinterpret the data got. As aforementioned earlier, participants themselves were selected using the purposive sampling technique to obtain persons relevant to the study. Details of the selection process are included in the sampling technique. These respondents/participants included 9 loyal listeners, 3 each from the 3 radio stations. These respondents had communication with the researcher before this research, and the researcher had a level of experience with music being regulated on the radio for audience satisfaction. It also included six (6) radio staff members, two (2) each from each of the three (3) radio stations, with whom the researcher had a communicative and direct contact relationship before this research, enabling the researcher to gain further insight into concrete details. These six (6) staff members included both top-level administrative staff and on-air personalities, and this is in consideration of the aims and study inquiries that were sought out in the research of this work.

Sampling Technique

The qualitative sample is sampled in a manner that operates within the frame of meaning that the researcher has in mind. With the study employing the purposive sampling technique, the frames of the researcher were more detailed and valid criteria were put in place to determine the individuals that were selected. Qualitative research does not pretend to discover context in dependent knowledge but aims at a deep understanding of phenomena in a specific context. Tracy (2013) observed that in qualitative research purposive sampling, the evidence chosen explains a particular issue within the existing parameters of research questions, goals, and other important details to be sought after.

The first group of participants who are loyal or ardent listeners of the given radio stations were chosen from specific areas in and around Port Harcourt and other communal areas of Rivers state, with the researcher keeping with activities of the ardent listeners through call logs into programs on the radio stations, contributions to these said programs and aiming to create a balance amongst the demography of the given participants. The sampling technique being purposive was evoked so while discussing as a group, the focus of the research could be easily and better understood, as in contrast to bringing in a random group of participants who have little or no inclination towards the programs on the given radio platforms. The first group of individuals is drawn from the three senatorial zones, which comprise Rivers East, Rivers South-East, and Rivers West.

With regard to the scope of this dissertation, an even spread was carried out for these listeners with age consents from eighteen (18) and above, as well as an almost even share of the different genders, which included eight (8) females and seven (7) males. The second group of respondents of this group discussion included individuals who were staff members of the given radio stations, while still involving the purposive sampling technique. These individuals were selected based on their prior relationship with the researcher and were selected based on their years of experience on these radio platforms and activities or line of work they handled as responsibilities in these radio stations. This is because some objectives of this given research required the experience and technical know-how of certain activities on the radio stations mentioned.

With these particular respondents consisting of four (4) males and two (2) females, these respondents were chosen purposively and specifically because they are staff members of these radio stations who are in charge of radio programming and what is approved or rejected on the radio space. In particular, the researcher evoked the purposive sampling technique with an aim to work within a frame of meaning and to obtain the most credible data from and for the research work itself.

Description of the Data Gathering Instrument

Qualitative research requires the researcher to be in the field and participate in the process. According to Tracy (2013), qualitative research methods in a research work must be first applied herein when describing who the data gathering instrument is. The researcher carrying out such work is the data gathering instrument, and as such, the researcher of this work is well-disciplined in communication and media studies, with a wide knowledge of this study. The researcher has a bachelor degree in International Relations and Diplomacy, the researcher is well seasoned with the research work and all

it has to entail, backed up alongside teachings and guidelines from his supervisor's pool of knowledge, the researcher brings to light data gathering through the qualitative method with a detailed approach.

Validity of the Study

Validity concerns in qualitative research refer to how truthful an account represents a social phenomenon, whereas reliability refers to its dependability. The foregoing shows that in qualitative research, the place of validity and reliability is recognized. This work carried out by the researcher expressed validity because the research design employed the use of a focus group discussion that implored the use of open-ended questions to evoke answers expressing truth and details, with three ardent and loyal listeners each from the three selected radio stations cut across the three senatorial zones of the state. Statements put into account for this research work carry truth because these listeners have remained loyal to the radio station. Alongside these listeners, two selected staff members each from the radio station with solid years of experience put statements into account through open-ended questions determining why music plays a big part in drawing the audience to their station.

Method of Data Presentation and Analysis

The empirical evidence that came from this study was analyzed using a summary of what participants said during the focus group discussion concerning the genres of music played, the policies put in place to aid engineering of audience through music, and to know if music being utilized by these radio stations drew more listeners to the work. The design focused on a group discussion involving a topic on music was shown or represented using illustrative quotes that were paramount to the course of this research work. Anderson (2010) stated that qualitative data are raw data and should be compiled and analyzed, not just listed. There should be an explanation of how the quotes were chosen and not just labeled.

With this correspondence, the research work was detailed through quotes such as 'genre of songs', 'type of policies', 'influence audience members', 'possible constraints' and more, because they bordered on details concrete to the objectives and questions sought out to solve the statement of the problem in this research work. Alongside these given details, important interaction in the focus group discussion for data discovery was obtained through open-ended questions that bordered on the objectives of the study in the discussion itself. The staff of the three radio stations alongside audience members as aforementioned were selected through a purposive sampling technique that bordered or hinged on the scope of the study, demographically and geographically. However, the participants lasted for a short while and commented freely due to the research design put in place for this study.

RESULTS

Presentation of the Focus Group Discussion

Genres of Music played to Engineer Audience by Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM in Rivers State

Genres of music used in audience engineering are important in evaluating the use of music for audience engineering by select radio stations in Rivers State. Different radio stations use different genres of music in audience engineering, such as hip-hop, blues, and gospel. To investigate the use of music for audience engineering by the three selected radio stations, the following questions were asked in the discussion and responses were easily evoked as they were open-ended questions. Staff participants,

especially the personalities that spoke on the airwaves, responded to this particular question as it hinged on the impact these genres of different songs played had engineered audience members toward their radio station.

What are the impacts of the genres of music played in audience engineering by Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM?

For Silverman and Marvasti, as they stated in their research work titled *Qualitative Research: A Comprehensive Guide* (2006), qualitative sampling hinges on the importance of what is to be sampled and how such will aid the explanation that researchers pursue. Whilst undergoing responses from the participants and their reactions to this question, a staff member, an air personality, with years of vast experience from Love FM stated that the genres of music being played had generally impacted the audience growth in the radio station, most especially gospel he stated that these different genres of music being played on the radio had caused a lot of listeners to tune in to the radio station requesting for their favourite tracks as well as a confirmation of more listeners being tuned in to various other programs like the One senate Show, which is yet politically inclined, on the radio station. He further added while concluding that music had a cultural right, as its messages being passed in content form could be as a metaphorical weapon to cause, inspire and impact change and was necessary in the promotion and protection of valuable mantras like that of legal human rights, also that music could help in the healing process of a given relationship or an activity an individual goes through, could dismantle walls of torn friendships and build boundaries while stirring a reconciliation and lastly could also serve as a tool to spread education in a positive light.

The staff member from Cool FM, an on-air personality as well, young and with years of experience and vigour, stated that music had impacted the way audiences tuned in to their radio stations more frequently than ever, already, with a radio station as Cool FM boasting as being a station that played trending afro-fused songs which top the musical charts, it was easily noticeable with the impact, even having superstars have a radio tour in the station to promote their songs and creative art, these often led the personality herself to consider herself a brand, as she stated that due to these impacts of the different genres of songs being played on the station, especially trending afro-fused songs, she made appearances' for shows, parties, social gatherings and more, thereby promoting herself as a brand and attracting a lot of promotion to the radio station. She further stated that around the world, music is being used as a vehicle for social change and bringing communities together. She added that the core of our everyday experience with music is that we use it to relax, express ourselves, come to terms with our emotions, and generally improve our well-being. In addition, it has evolved into a tool for healing and self-expression, often dictating how we as individuals take steps to impact society.

Lastly, the OAP from Wazobia FM, who also doubled as an administrative staff in the radio station, stated that music and its various genres had impacted and shaped cultures and societies around the world; speaking from a very general perspective, these genres of music had also helped to pass cultural information from one generation to another, speaking in direct relation to that statement, he stated that elderly individuals who enjoyed classic songs and golden oldies had confirmed through calls and special song requests that they equally enjoyed the new trending songs popularized by the youths, and

so is the reverse the case as well. He concluded that these different genres of music also had the power to alter one's mood, change perceptions, and inspire change. He maintained that music was an essential aspect of all human civilizations and had the power to emotionally affect society. He further concluded that music aided social bonding as they were tied, especially during crucial times of conflict when other lines of communication had proven to be a challenge.

Types of Policies on Music Used by Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM

The following questions concerning the different types of policies that these radio stations used musically to draw the audience toward their different radio stations were asked in the discussion. The responses were evoked easily as they were open-ended questions asked. Staff participants, those that held top managerial positions and had a prior relationship communicatively with the researcher, responded to this particular question as it hinged on the policies of governmental and financial genres of different songs used in played drawing audience members toward their radio station.

In response to the above question, the top managerial staff from Cool FM, having had years of managerial experience in different sectors of radio journalism, stated that policies on music utilized by the radio station were likened to how performing musicians prepare for a recital, not just by practising the piece from start to finish but by concentrating on small sections of it at a time until they achieve mastery. In this sense, on a radio platform such as CoolFM, she stated that musical policies were put in place to ensure that raving songs or trending songs were being played on the radio station at least 3-5 times a day to draw the audience to their station, through music schedule programs as 'Song of the Week', 'Drivetime Show', that song or particular catchy phrase in the content of the song their listeners remained glued to their station and tuned in to other programs on the radio station, thereby showing signs in an increase in audience traction, as well as putting them as one of the youth-inclined, urban-driven radio stations in the state.

The next participant, equally an administrative staff of Love FM and personnel manager with years of experience as well, stated in a conclusive approach, policies on music are intentional because it involved an act of thinking and putting into practice, areas of improvement and means to achieve goals for every task; the necessity to be responsive with immediate feedback and repeating each mastery to achieve goals as moments pass, doing all this in accordance to the given governmental laws that regulate the radio journalistic structure, with this being said, he pointed out that policies were put out to utilize music to draw audience to activities on the radio station, and it was not just musically bordering on the station, or financially telling but also governmental because as much as songs could be played to draw audience to the radio station, they had to be played in accordance with the regulating body governing radio airwaves in the federation, being the national broadcasting commission (NBC), as such these songs had to be played with caution, excluding explicit content so as not to attract fines or charges from the regulating commission, these in turn draw specific groups of audience who appreciate songs being played on the station, devoid of explicit content, with gospel music playing a lead genre in that category, he conclusively maintained that positive results drawn from utilizing music policies to draw audience to their station had to be followed with consistent efforts as well.

The top managerial individual from Wazobia FM, with years of executive experience as well, also indicated that music policies were like powerful database metrics on YouTube that give out information on what happens to a YouTube video or song if it uses certain original or copyrighted sounds or vocals to put out its content. In this context, policies utilized were broken down not just musically but also financially to gain traction and financial stability as a radio platform. These policies may be musical, but they are drawn up to attract finance toward the radio station. In a primal example, he stated that financial policies were put in through musical utilization to draw audience toward the show, citing an example where a classic gospel artist has an interview on the radio platform. As much as the gospel artist may be raving at the moment, he or she would also need the promotional coverage and the communal grass root reach that a radio station platform provides. As such, a financial levy would be put in place to charge the artist for their coverage, while likewise drawing audience to their station, the reason being that a big named raving artist had graced the radio station.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Objective 1: Determine the genres of music played to engineer audiences by Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM

The analysis and discussions within this research were concluded on the findings of the inquiries in the study. In the first objective analysed, it was discovered that the genres of music, differently put, had been played to engineer audiences toward their radio stations. According to McDonald and Kreutz in their book titled *Music, Health and Wellbeing* (2013), they affirm that creativity to communicate grammatically with individuals both far and wide without stating words, arrangement of letters, or even active participation motor skills are inborn before conception and in childhood. It is from these inborn harmonious tunes that different genres of music are played as a way of life and as such the ever-evolving concept that begins from little detail to a component of one's memories or life. This citation then showed that music and the genre specifically play a key role in attaining the attention of an individual. On radio, this same role is put in place to enable listeners to grow a love for content being put out by the particular given radio station. As such, it was found that for a radio station such as Cool FM, trending genres of music remain a weapon or tool of mass engineering of audience towards the radio station. The reason being that a huge amount and audience target of its relative audience are youthful individuals or young, growing adults who are not generally concerned with activities that are musically inclined but instead gravitate towards new, trending songs that currently occupy charting positions on the new age, technological, musical platforms, just as the staff member from the radio station had stated that playing trending afro-fused songs which top the musical charts, had made it easily noticeable with the impact, even having musical superstars have a radio tour in the station to promote their songs and creative art.

These often led the personality herself to consider herself a brand, as she stated that due to these impacts of the different genres of songs being played on the station, especially trending afro-fused songs, she made appearances' for shows, parties, social gatherings, and more, thereby promoting herself as a brand and attracting a lot of promotion to the radio station. Further corroborating, this is supported by the views of Patel in his book, *Music, Language and the Brain* (2009), who said music

plays a role in attracting a youthful audience toward a growing listenership be it on radio or otherwise, and this is because music plays the role of growth and elevation in a growing mind as well as other demographic age grades of human civilization, and as such has an impact on a growing audience.

Love FM had a wide genre of musicals played but with a direct growth on gospel music, with the structure and ownership of the radio station being controlled by a private individual and unlike the structure of Cool FM and Wazobia FM being a conglomerate with divided ownership and each battling for supremacy, Love FM used a lot of gospel music to keep their audience engaged as its company name alias is also known as Family Love FM, with the response from the participants who stated that the genres of music being played generally impacted the audience growth in the radio station, most especially gospel which had led to a lot of listeners tuning in to the radio station to request for their favourite gospel tracks as well as a confirmation of more listeners being tuned in to various other programs like the One senate Show, which is yet politically inclined, on the radio station.

Further stamping on this finding, McDonald (2013), in his aforementioned book, reiterates that music used in drawing an audience leaves an effect on them. In this case, gospel music being known to channel the morality of the listener further shows the impact such a genre has on its audience as a strong part of its major listeners are spiritual leaders and theologians, and most of its listenership is in a family setting where kids as well as adults gather around to hear the type of songs being played on the radio. The genres of music being played on Wazobia FM were mostly traditional Afro beats of the likes of Fela Anikulakpo Kuti and King Sunny Ade, as well as a combination of classic music and highlife.

These genres of music also helped to pass cultural information from one generation to another, spe. Speaking direct relation to that statement, the participant who even answered the question stated that older adults individuals who enjoyed classic songs and golden oldies had confirmed through calls and special song requests that they equally enjoyed the new trending songs popularized by the youths, and so is the reverse the case as well, and this is because majority of its audience are the average Rivers State individual and with the standard of living cut across all ties. This further shows what Nancy Adler, a renowned psychologist, states in her book titled, *Managing Cross-Cultural Transitions*, (1981): music is ever evolving, cutting across the characteristics of the various listeners, because it plays a paramount function within the formation of the growing audience. These findings of this particular objective are in agreement with the active audience theory, which states that the media audience does not just take in content without paying close attention, but their oratory skills are at full alert and such involvement draws more attention through the audience to the radio station as regards the three radio stations in this research work.

Objective 2: What types of deliberate policies on music are being utilized by Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM?

The conclusions drawn from this research show that these genres of music being played on radio stations had certain policies attached to their airplay to draw audiences through to their radio station. A station such as Wazobia FM puts out musical content within a particular timeframe to keep their listeners glued to their station, a classic tune or an early song from a highlife pioneer like Rex Lawson being played at noon with a creative tag like the Noon Drive has proven a musical policy that has kept

their listeners glued to their station even with some requests from listeners as they raised opinions for their musical choices to be played on air; this is in cognizance with what the top managerial individual from Wazobia FM, with years of executive experience as well stated.

He further indicated that music policies were like powerful database metrics on YouTube that provide information on what happens to a YouTube video or song if it uses certain original or copyrighted sounds or vocals to put out its content. These policies used were broken down not just musically, but financially as well to gain traction and financial stability as a radio platform. These policies may be musical, but they are drawn up to attract finance toward the radio station. In a primal example, he stated that financial policies were put in through musical use to draw the audience toward the show, citing an example where a classic gospel artist has an interview on the radio platform. As much as the gospel artist may be raving at the moment, he or she would also need the promotional coverage and the communal grass root reach that a radio station platform provides. As such, a financial levy would be put in place to charge the artist for their coverage, while likewise drawing the audience to their station. The reason was that a big-name raving artist had graced the radio station. Likewise, it was also established that a radio station like Love FM used certain musical incentives like Gospel Song of the Week, which had proven to keep listeners glued to their station as audiences would send in requests for their favourite gospel songs of the week. This, in turn, had this financial advantage toward the radio stations because the station could set a price for songs worthy of the songs of the week tag and ardent listeners would lobby financially and pay. As a privately owned radio station, it was a policy that enabled the room for gospel music to saturate the airwaves and draw in financial gains that would benefit the station as it is a privately run company with little or no support from the state's radio governing body. This in turn agreed with the research question that was answered by the staff participant of the radio station who said the policies on music were intentional because it involved an act of thinking and putting into practice areas of improvement and means to achieve goals for every task; the necessity to be responsive with immediate feedback and repeating each mastery to achieve goals as moments passed while doing all this in accordance with the given governmental laws that regulate the radio journalistic structure. It was not just musically bordering on the station, or financially telling but also governmental because as much as songs could be played to draw the audience to the radio station, they had to be played by the regulating body governing radio airwaves in the federation.

The National Broadcasting Commission (NBC), as such, required these songs to be played with caution, excluding explicit content so as not to attract fines or charges from the regulating commission, in turn drawing specific groups of audience who appreciate songs being played on the station, devoid of explicit content, with gospel music playing a lead genre in that category. Cool FM as a radio station had policies on music which were put in place to ensure that raving songs or trending songs were being played on the radio station at least 3-5 times a day to draw the audience to their station, as with regard to the response by the staff of the radio station, through music schedule programs such as 'Song of the Week', and the 'Drive time Show' that song or particular catchy phrase in the content of the song kept their listeners remained glued to their station, leading them to tune in to other programs on the radio station,

thereby showing signs in an increase in audience traction, as well as marking them as one of the youth-inclined, urban-driven radio stations in the state.

CONCLUSION

The study also concluded that the types of deliberate policies on music used by Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM were financial, governmental, and creatively motivated to attract and keep listeners loyal to their radio stations. The three stations also used technological platforms such as the social media space, where information on what happens to a song or video is elaborated, and it is also permissible if it uses certain samples of copyrighted songs or the original score itself. The conclusion of this research also concluded that most participants believed that Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM improved audience engineering by playing their favorite songs to keep listeners tuned in and by enhancing social skills in society. Owing to the excellent wellness, it has, especially in youngsters, it also increases cognitive development and bodily vigor in people. The study also concluded that the three radio stations' possible constraints in audience engineering include introducing songs that are not appropriate for radio play in terms of language and content, which may eventually cause listeners to become distracted and leave such stations for another with a better ambience. In addition, having a bad power supply or a weak frequency transmission may eventually cause listeners to become disinterested and go to another station with a better atmosphere.

Recommendations

Based on the validity and reliability of the data within this research, the due recommendations were approved to enhance the use of music for audience engineering by Love FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM stations using a comparative evaluation.

1. There is a need for radio stations to choose appropriate genres of music that will facilitate audience engineering.
2. Media houses/radio stations should learn to take deliberate policies that will help them in audience engineering, especially by regularly reviewing the music played by their stations.

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